

**NOVEL EVALUATION METHOD TO IDENTIFY CRITICAL SEGMENTS OF
URBAN TRANSPORTATION NETWORK BY INTRODUCING A NEW
DEFINITION FOR IMPOTANCE INDEX**

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ABSTRACT

Frequent disruptive incidents occur over and over in transportation networks which influence the networks' efficiency. It is obvious that the effects of disruptions to different links can lead to different consequences in the networks. This paper tries to analyze these effects by introducing a methodology to identify the critical links of an urban highway network. This new approach is based on determining the significance of network's links called Importance Index in the present paper; the higher importance index each link has, the more effects has on the network and the highest value of value of importance index is related to critical link; "accessibility" is what helps us to calculate importance index. After occurring disruption, by using single-link failure mechanism traffic is assigned by Aimsun software based on "Capacity-Restrained Traffic Assignment" Method, and travel-cost is calculated by using three factors including travel time, DDHV and link length, then shortest-path-trees for all nodes are plotted by employing Moor algorithm and C++ coding. This paper takes Tehran district 4 transportation network as the case study. The results show that the north side of Hengam Ave is the most important part of the network study.

KEYWORDS:

Accessibility, Importance Index, Critical Link, urban highways network, Capacity-Restrained Traffic Assignment, Single Link Failure Mechanism

INTRODUCTION

Along with spectacular advances in science and technology, the concept of transportation's influences on people's life has been gaining publicity over the past couple of decades. It is, in this regard, stated that transportation play crucial role in people's daily-life and due to its diverse roles, their health, income and social-life are utterly influenced by transportation. There are wide ranges of factors from unforeseen events like accidents and road repairs to social events like fair and sport competitions which affect transportation's efficiency in urban areas, but among them frequent natural disasters that often occur in transportation systems cause the major damage to this system[1].

Earthquakes, flooding and blizzard are factors which influence transportation system dramatically and can have both long-term and short-term effects on the network. Subsequent short-term effects of natural disasters are what is analyzed in this paper. The main purpose of this research is related to identifying the segments (link or links) which impose the most cost on network during natural disasters. For fulfilling this aim we use "Single-Link Failure Mechanism" introduced by Jenelius [2]. This method is practical for low-intensity natural disasters which influence a few links; however, for natural disasters like earthquakes that influence more than one link, "Multiple-link Failure Mechanism" should be employed; these catastrophes mainly have long-term effects on the network [3].

Research that analyze the effects of natural disasters on transportation network are entangled with the concept of *transportation vulnerability* introduced by Berdica (2002) - vulnerability was defined as potential consequences of a disastrous event on system performance-; therefore, it should be regarded as a new concept in transportation[4]. UNISDR (2009) defined vulnerability as the elements involved in making a system susceptible to the damages incurred by a hazard, representing a negative indicator of system performance during

disaster management [5]. Entropy, also known as Shannon-Weaver Index (shown as Equation 1) represents one of the major diversity indicators, where H is the value of diversity, P_i represents the proportion of the population of species i to the total population (shown as Equation 2), and n_i denotes the number of individuals belonging to species i [6].

$$H = - \sum_i P_i * \ln P_i$$

Eq1

$$P_i = \frac{n_i}{\sum n_i}$$

Eq2

Hsieh (2014) applied the transport diversity [7]. developed by Feng and Hsieh [6] to evaluate the port vulnerability by modifying Equations 1 and 2 into Equations 3 and 4, respectively, in which H_l indicates the integrated vulnerability of port l and P_{kl} denotes the achievement probability of each vulnerability factor k for port l .

$$H_l = - \sum_k P_{kl} * \ln P_{kl}$$

Eq 3

$$P_{kl} = \frac{n_{kl}}{\sum n_{kl}}$$

Eq 4

$$n_{kl} = \frac{O_k^{Max} - U_{kl}}{O_k^{Max} - U_k^{Min}}$$

Eq5

Equation 5 indicates the achievement between the expected goal and present vulnerability level of the factor k in operations of port l , in which O_k^{Max} and O_k^{Min} represent the maximum and minimum levels of factor k , respectively, and U_{kl} is the present value of vulnerability factor k for port l . The normalised value prevents indicator gaps resulting from differences in unit scale.

Redundancy is a common term in transportation vulnerability introduced by Jenelius and it helped to develop a method to determine the importance of links, once the network encounter incidents [8].

Wang in an article (Evaluation Method for Highway Network's Resistant Ability against Natural Disasters and the Conclusion Analysis), investigated different factors role in Hangzhou road network resistance ability against natural disasters by FUZZY hierarchy method. In this study three "network structure", "network stability" and "maintenance management" factors were used as main factors and sub factors as density, continuity, access, level of service and reliability were used for modeling [9].

Cheng investigated Taiwan road network vulnerability after disaster (earth quick) occurrence. In the mentioned investigation, prioritization and identifying effective factors on failure intensity of road network was studied by assuming that rescue operation after disaster is of paramount importance to officials [10].

Nogala studied part of Ireland road network. In this study, assessment of inherent vulnerability of traffic network was implemented by collection of measurable indexes like accessibility and reliability. They presented a new multivariate method which could estimate inherent vulnerability and possible relation of that with accessibility and reliability indexes [11].

METHODOLOGY

Graph Theory

At the first stage, studied network should be considered as a set of vertices and edges (according to graph theory), then the network should be summarized because it is so costly to involve all nodes and links in study.

After summarizing the network, connected and disconnected links should be distinguished by the definition uttered by Bababeik. If failure in a specific link leads to disconnecting between any pair of origin-destination, this link would be called "disconnected". In other word, there is no replacement for disconnected links, even by spending more time and cost[12]. Hence, these links are more important than connected links which have replacement and consequently they have higher *Importance Index* than connected links. a_1, a_2, a_3, a_7 in figure 1 are disconnected links and a_3, a_4, a_5 are connected links

Fig. 1. Connected and unconnected links

Travel cost

Travel-cost refers to people traveling in network by one form of transportation which could be analyzed as a financial or non-financial matter; however it is usually comparable with travel-time in transportation studies and by increasing travel-time, travel-cost correspondingly would increase. It is obvious that chaos on the roads is another effective factor in travel cost, because it can increase travel-time indirectly [13]. Travel-cost is a multiple of travel-time and a weight coefficient of origin-distention [14]. According to the mentioned definitions concerning travel-cost, a new formula is introduced in present paper which supports both cited theory.

In this study, the Directional Design Hour Volume (DDHV) is considered as the relative weight of each pair of origin-destination link, and then is divided by link length to eliminate the effect of link length on travel time.

According to presented descriptions, we should calculate travel cost of all links for calculating network robustness index by following equation:

$$\text{Eq6} \quad C_{ij} = \frac{t_{ij} \cdot DDHV_{ij}}{L_{ij}}$$

C_{ij} : travel cost function from i (origin) to j (destination) according to arc length

t_{ij} : travel time from i to j

$DDHV_{ij}$: Directional Design Hour Volume from node i to j (veh/h)

L_{ij} : ij arc length (m)

This cost should be calculated under normal circumstances (before crisis) for all links of the network. To do this; by utilizing the moor algorithm, shortest-path for the networks' nodes are drawn. In the other words; the shortest-path tree must be drawn for all of the networks' nodes and afterwards travel cost for all nodes is calculated by using the corresponding the shortest-path tree.

$$\text{Eq 7} \quad C_i^{(n)} = \sum_i^n C_{ij}$$

$C_i^{(n)}$: Travel cost from node i (under normal circumstances)

After calculating the assignment cost for all nodes, by summing the travel cost of all networks' nodes; the total travel cost (under normal circumstances) will be calculated.

$$\text{Eq 8} \quad C_{\text{total}}^{(n)} = \sum_i^n C_i$$

$C_{\text{total}}^{(n)}$: Total Travel cost (under normal circumstances)

Shortest-path-trees

The shortest path trees between origins and destinations are plotted according to the concept of Moor Algorithm. Due to considerable amount of mathematical calculations for plating shortest-path-tree for all nodes, the algorithm is coded by C++.

Traffic assignment

Capacity-Restrained Traffic Assignment method is employed in this study for assigning traffic by using Aimsun software and traffic maps provided by Research Institute of the Municipality of Tehran and Traffic Maps which are available on google map. Demand rate differ from hour to hour during a day; so, PHV (peak hour volume) in weekdays is used as input data for modeling.

Many different capacity restraint equations have been developed and tested and are available for use. There are two basic characteristics common to capacity restraint models; (i) they are non-linear relationships and (ii) they use the volume-capacity ratio or v/c as a common factor. The underlying premise of a capacity restraint model is that the travel time on any link is related to the traffic volume on that link. This is analogous to the level of service (LOS) criterion, where LOS A corresponds to a low v/c and a higher vehicle speed. LOS E and the corresponding v/c = 1 represents capacity[15].

Capacity restraint models assign traffic to possible routes in an iterative manner:

1. A portion of the total traffic volume is assigned to the link with the shortest travel time.
2. Travel times for all possible links are calculated again, since volumes have changed.
3. Another portion of the traffic volume remaining to be assigned is allocated to the link that now has the shortest travel time.
4. The travel time for all links are calculated and revised if changes result.
5. The process of incremental assignments, followed by calculation of revised shortest travel times, by link, continues until all trips have been assigned.

The capacity restraint model used by FHWA is applied in an iterative manner. The adjusted link speed and/or its associated travel impedance is computed using the following capacity restraint function[16]:

$$\text{Eq 9} \quad T = T_o [1 + 0.15(V/C)^4]$$

Where:

T = balance travel time (at which traffic V can travel on a highway segment)

T_o = free flow travel time: observed travel time (at practical capacity) times 0.87

V = assigned volume

C = practical capacity

Accessibility Index Elaboration**Weight Assigned to Each Travel Mode (W_m)**

As already mentioned, an important premise in the elaboration of the proposed accessibility index is that each mode of transport has a degree of importance in facilitating displacements according to their capacity and speed. Thus, for each modal, a weight was calculated to be used in the calculation of the indicators, a weight was also calculated for each mode of integration between buses and other modes.

For the calculation of the weight for each mode of public transportation, the criteria used to assign greater or lesser weight refer to the capacity and speed of each modal, thus the following equation was used[17]:

$$\text{Eq 10} \quad W_{msi} = \left(\frac{C_m}{C_{max}} + \frac{V_m}{V_{max}} \right) \div 2$$

Where:

W_{msi} : Weight assigned to the modal (without integration);

C_m : Modal average capacity;

C_{max} : Medium capacity of the largest capacity modality;

V_m : Average speed of the modal;

V_{max} : Average speed of the highest speed mode. The methodology adopted in this paper is an intensive literature review on the various types of technologies for solid waste disposal.

In traditional composting systems, organic material is just piled together and then left for a year; while more elaborated composting systems take 2 to 3 weeks for complete decomposition. This system necessitates that the materials to compost be chopped up, into small pieces, and carbon (C) to nitrogen (N) ratio not exceeding 30:1. It

CASE STUDY: THE 4th DISTRICT OF TEHRAN

In this paper, highways network of the 4th district of Tehran is studied as a case. This highway network is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Tehran district 4 highways network

In accordance with the hierarchy of modeling presented in the previous section, at the first Step: shown the network based on graph theory.(Fig.3)

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In the figure below; all of the the links' travel cost shown on the network graph.(Fig.4)

Fig. 4. The travel cost of each link under normal circumstances

After calculating the travel cost of each link; by using all-or-nothing assign method and moor algorithm, the shortest-path tree to was drawn for all nodes (Figure 5).

Fig. 5. The shortest-path tree of all nodes under normal circumstances

After assigning of the nodes, Due to the existing routes of shortest-path trees and use of (Equation 2); the cost of traveling from one node to other nodes is calculated. The following table shows the cost of travel from node A (see table 2).

Table 2. Assignment of node A and its cost

Source(i)	Destination(j)	Route: Traveled link(s)	Cost of travel	summation
A	B	AB	125	125
	C	AB-BC	125+98	223
	D	AB-BC-CD	125+98+104	327
	E	AE	92	92
	F	AE-AF	92+125	217
	G	AE-EF-FG	92+125+118	335
	H	AB-BC-CD-DH	125+98+104+130	457
	I	AE-EI	92+198	290
	J	AE-EF-FJ	92+125+94	311
	K	AE-EF-FJ-JK	92+125+94+96	407
L	AE-EF-FJ-JK-KL	92+125+94+96+114	521	

$$C_i^{(n)} = \sum_i^n C_{ij} \quad ; \quad C_A^{(n)} = C_{AB} + C_{AC} + C_{AD} + C_{AE} + C_{AF} + C_{AG} + C_{AH} + C_{AI} + C_{AJ} + C_{AK} + C_{AL}$$

 $5 + 223 + 327 + 92 + 217 + 335 + 457 + 290 + 311 + 407 + 521 = 3305$

Similarly, this cost is calculated for other network nodes. Subsequently, in accordance with (Equation 4) the sum of these costs, the total travel of Network will be calculated that is visible in the table below (see table 2).

Table 3. The travel cost from a node to another nodes under normal circumstances

sum	$C_L^{(n)}$	$C_K^{(n)}$	$C_J^{(n)}$	$C_I^{(n)}$	$C_H^{(n)}$	$C_G^{(n)}$	$C_F^{(n)}$	$C_E^{(n)}$	$C_D^{(n)}$	$C_C^{(n)}$	$C_B^{(n)}$	$C_A^{(n)}$
35197	3349	2822	2465	3842	3162	2533	2125	2975	3366	2737	2516	3305

Now we can by removing a link of Network, calculating the NRI. But to maximize the NRI, we need to determine the importance index for each link and finding the critical link.

For this purpose; by using the shortest-path-tree and access routes to the nodes, we compiled the following table. The numbers that inserted in front of each link, Represents the number of accesses that provided in each assignment to other nodes. For example, on assignment of node A, AB link provides access to other 9 nodes , or on assignment of node E, IJ link does not provide access to any node (see table 4). According to the description provided, it is obviously, the larger the sum of the numbers in front of each link, the link has a greater role in the assignment of network. Therefore, the largest number of table is the number that is corresponding to critical link.

Table 4. Ranking of the link importance

SUM	L	K	J	I	H	G	F	E	D	C	B	A	
18	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	9	AB
28	0	0	2	2	2	0	2	2	6	6	3	3	BC
25	1	0	1	1	3	1	1	1	9	3	2	2	CD
19	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	9	1	1	2	0	EF
16	0	0	1	1	2	6	2	2	0	0	1	1	FG
8	1	0	0	0	3	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	GH
17	1	1	1	9	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	IJ
28	6	6	3	3	2	0	2	2	0	0	2	2	JK
21	7	3	2	2	3	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	KL
4	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	EA
5	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	EI
40	2	2	4	3	0	2	4	3	4	4	7	5	FB
39	4	4	7	5	0	2	4	3	2	2	3	3	FJ
7	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	2	0	0	CG
5	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	GK
13	2	1	0	0	4	0	0	0	2	2	1	1	HD
15	4	2	1	1	4	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	HL

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According to the above table, FB link is critical link of the network. Assuming failure in the critical link, by removing this link of network; calculated the travel cost again. According to, absence of FB link, and spreading its traffic on nearby links; drawing a new network graph for disaster time(Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Travel cost in disaster time

Due to occurrence the changes in links' travel cost and absence of FB link, nodes assignment will be changed (Except node H, because there wasn't the FB link in the shortest-path tree of node H). (Fig. 7)

Fig. 7. The shortest-path tree of all nodes in disaster time

by using equation(3), the travel cost for each nodes will be calculated in disaster time, afterwards by summing these costs, the network travel cost will be calculated that is visible in following table.(see table 5).

Table 5. The travel cost from a node to another nodes under normal circumstances

SUM $C_{total}^{(n)}$	$C_L^{(n)}$	$C_K^{(n)}$	$C_J^{(n)}$	$C_I^{(n)}$	$C_H^{(n)}$	$C_G^{(n)}$	$C_F^{(n)}$	$C_E^{(n)}$	$C_D^{(n)}$	$C_C^{(n)}$	$C_B^{(n)}$	$C_A^{(n)}$
40392	3519	3128	3196	4216	3162	2771	2839	3315	3570	3332	3655	3689

According to the tables 3 and 2:

$$C_{total}^{(d)} = 40392$$

$$C_{total}^{(n)} = 35197$$

Which represent the travel cost in disaster time/ travel cost under normal circumstances.

The final step is to calculate the network robustness index, by using equation(4):

$$NRI = 40392 - 35197 \longrightarrow NRI = 5195$$

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

These days, preponderance researchers have done research about long-term catastrophic disruptions, while the probability of occurrence these events are less than the short-term events. Due to the rise in number of accidents, maintenance operations and other events that could reduce the capacity of the network during a day, study about the effects of short-term events on the network is essential. So in this paper, by focusing on the disruptions with short-time effects, modern methods are introduced for evaluating the importance index, identifying the "critical link" of networks and finally calculating the network robustness index (NRI).

If policy makers and transport analyst want to design a robust urban transportation network against natural disasters, they must have enough information concerning the network they are study on. Firstly, the critical segments of networks should be determined, and this paper tried to present a framework for analyzing the importance of links and robustness of urban transportation network which can lead to identifying the critical segments.

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